

DURABILITY OF FIBER SPLAY ANCHORS IN BOND-CRITICAL CFRP UNDER ACCELERATED HYGROTHERMAL CONDITIONING

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ABSTRACT

This research investigated the durability of fiber anchors in bond-critical CFRP systems for concrete structures. While the durability of CFRP and CFRP-concrete bond is well-studied, the durability of fiber anchors in typical bond-critical applications remains unexplored. To address this gap, fiber anchors were tested in 152×152×508-mm notched beams strengthened with CFRP. Accelerated conditioning involved 3,000 hours of water immersion at 50 °C. Results revealed up to 24% capacity loss in specimens with anchor rupture as the failure mode, while no capacity loss was observed in specimens failing due to flexural CFRP rupture.

KEYWORDS

Durability; bond; fiber splay anchors; hygrothermal; concrete.

INTRODUCTION

To enhance the strain utilization of externally bonded CFRP, various types of anchors can be utilized. These include U-wraps (Tatar et al. 2023), patch anchors (Kalfat and Al-Mahaidi 2014), and fiber splay anchors (del Rey Castillo 2019). Fiber splay anchors are commonly favored when other types of anchors cannot be used due to geometric constraints or limited space availability. These anchors improve the utilization of CFRP strain and can be strategically positioned to promote a pseudoductile failure mode in the strengthened member. The fiber splay anchors consist of an anchor dowel and an anchor fan (refer to Figure 1). The dowel is embedded into the concrete, while the anchor fan spreads out over the width of the anchored CFRP laminate.

Previous research (Sun et al. 2016) has examined the impact of varying splay angles and anchor diameters while maintaining a constant embedment depth. The study recommended splay angles no greater than 64 degrees to ensure the complete development of the anchored CFRP laminate. Additionally, the researchers suggested a minimum "anchorage material ratio" of 2.

Previous studies (Tatar and Hamilton 2016; Milev and Tatar 2021) have established that the bond between CFRP and concrete can deteriorate under hygrothermal conditions. While it has been observed that CFRP composites are generally resistant to hygrothermal effects (Cromwell et al. 2011), no studies have specifically examined the performance of an anchored bond-critical CFRP system. Considering that carbon fiber splay anchors are commonly used in applications that may expose them to harsh environments, it is crucial to assess the durability of these anchors under such conditions. Therefore, this research aimed to investigate the impact of accelerated conditioning, involving water immersion at 50°C for 3,000 hours (following ACI 2015 recommendations), on the strength of the anchors. The experimental program employed notched concrete beam specimens, similar to those recommended by ACI (2015).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Program

The experimental program consisted of testing notched concrete beams measuring 508×152×152 mm (l×w×h), reinforced with flexural CFRP at the tension face (Figure 2). The beams were split into two test group—a group kept in standard laboratory conditions (23 ± 3 °C and relative humidity of $50 \pm 10\%$) or “SLC,” and those subjected to accelerated conditioning protocol by continuous immersion in potable water at 50 ± 3 °C for 3,000 hours or “ACP”, per ACI (2015). In addition, the test program evaluated the effect of anchorage ratio (AR, defined as the ratio of equivalent laminate area or an anchor to flexural laminate area) and CFRP-concrete bond condition (bonded vs. unbonded). The test program is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Test matrix.

Conditioning	Carbon Fiber Splay Anchors (A or UA)	Bonded or Unbonded (B or UB)	Anchor Diameter (mm)	AR	Replicates
SLC	-	-	-		3
	UA	B	-		3
	A	B	6.4	1.06	3
			9.5	1.41	3
			12.7	2.0	3
		UB	6.4	1.06	3
			9.5	1.41	3
			12.7	2.0	3
	ACP	-	-	-	
UA		B	-		3
A		B	6.4	1.06	3
			9.5	1.41	3
			12.7	2.0	3
		UB	6.4	1.06	3
			9.5	1.41	3
			12.7	2.0	3

Materials

Concrete with a design compressive strength of 55 MPa was supplied by a ready-mix plant in Delaware, USA. The mix with a w/cm ratio of 0.35 consisted of Portland cement and slag in a 0.40:0.60 weight ratio, coarse aggregate and fine aggregate in a 0.63:0.37 weight ratio, and an air-entraining admixture. Since the focus of the study was on fiber anchor durability rather than CFRP-concrete bond durability, slag and air entraining were implemented to ensure durable CFRP-concrete adhesive bonding. Slag reduces the permeability of cement paste, thus resulting in improved durability of the substrate while the air entraining admixture ensures superior wetting of the substrate with the adhesive and promotes mechanical interlock.

Flexural CFRP and fiber anchors were fabricated from a 393 g/m² unidirectional carbon fiber fabric and an ambient cured epoxy resin. Manufacturer-reported tensile strength and modulus of fibers is 3.79 and 230 GPa, respectively. The reported tensile strength and modulus of the resulting CFRP composite were 986 MPa and 95.8 GPa, respectively. Epoxy adhesive used as a concrete substrate primer and saturating resin consisted of Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (BADGE) and an amine-based hardener. Putty adhesive consisted of the same based resin filled with 5.4 wt% of silica fume.

Table 2. Properties of epoxy adhesive reported by the manufacturer following 72 hours post cure at 60 °C.

Property	Typical Test Value
Glass Transition Temperature (T _g)	180 °F (82 °C)
Tensile Strength	10,500 psi (72.4 MPa)
Tensile Modulus	461,000 psi (3.18 GPa)
Elongation Percent	5%
Flexural Strength	17,900 psi (123.4 MPa)
Flexural Modulus	452,000 psi (3.12 GPa)

Specimen Fabrication

Concrete beam preparation involved several steps before CFRP and anchors were installed. Anchor holes were first drilled to a depth of 102 mm. The anchor hole diameter was roughly 1.4 times the nominal diameter of the anchor. To minimize stress concentrations, anchor holes were chamfered to a 12.5-mm radius (Figure 3a). Similarly, corners of the beams with shear CFRP wraps were chamfered to a 12.5-mm radius (Figure 3b). Beam specimens were then notched using a diamond saw (Figure 3c).

Finally, all surfaces having CFRP were sandblasted using coal slag blasting media to an ICRI CSP 3 (Figure 3d). This last step was omitted in beams where flexural CFRP was unbonded. Instead, Teflon tape was used to act as a bond breaker.

A coat of neat epoxy was applied with a paint roller to all surfaces of beams where CFRP was to be installed. This was followed by applying a thin layer of putty with a plastic spatula. In beams with fiber anchors, a syringe was used to fill anchor holes approximately half-way with putty. CFRP sheets (saturated in a 1:1 weight ratio of fibers to epoxy) were then placed on the concrete surface. In beams with fiber anchors, fiber tows were carefully separated and saturated fiber anchors were then inserted into the holes with an anchor embedment tool, followed by splaying anchors to a 60° angle, as shown in Figure 3e. This resulted in an 89-mm long splay, which was then covered with a 100×100 mm CFRP patch (Figure 3f), as recommended by the manufacturer.

Figure 3. Specimen preparation: (a) chamfered anchor hole; (b) chamfered beam corners; (c) notch at beam midspan; (d) concrete surface following sandblasting; (e) CFRP strip with fiber anchors on the tension face of a beam; and (f) CFRP patch placed over the anchor.

Experimental Procedures

The three-point bending beam test setup is shown in Figure 2b. All beams were instrumented with two LVDTs placed at midspan on each side of the beam, and a 3-mm strain gauge placed on the CFRP underneath the notch. Beams were tested in an Instron universal testing machine at a constant displacement rate of 1.2 mm/min, ensuring that all strengthened specimens failed within 3 to 5 minutes, as recommended by ACI (2015).

Accelerated conditioning was conducted by immersing specimens in a water tank equipped with a circulation water heater and a pump. The specimens were conditioned at 50 ± 3 °C for 3,000 hours. Temperature was monitored continuously with an immersion thermometer. All SLC and ACP beams were post-conditioned in a moist room at 23 ± 2 °C for 24 hours, then tested within 2 to 5 hours following the 24-hour post-conditioning per ACI (2015).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4 illustrates the typical load-displacement behaviors of different test beam groups. The unstrengthened beams demonstrated linear-elastic behavior until failure, which occurred when tensile cracking emerged at the notch (P_{cr}). The strengthened unanchored beams experienced debonding right after cracking at the notch, evidenced by a load plateau in the load-displacement plot.

For specimens with bonded anchored CFRP, debonding occurred subsequent to reaching P_{cr} . This was followed by a relatively short debonding plateau, after which the anchors engaged, leading to an increase in stiffness until specimen failure. The failure was initiated either by anchor failure or CFRP rupture. In the case of anchored specimens with unbonded CFRP, different behavior was observed. Due to the absence of bond between the CFRP and concrete, immediate slip occurred after reaching P_{cr} , resulting in a sharp decrease in force. Anchor engagement then took place, leading to an increase in stiffness. Specimens with unbonded CFRP exhibited failure either through anchor rupture or CFRP rupture.

Figure 4. Typical load-displacement behavior of test specimens in different test groups.

Standard Laboratory Conditioning (SLC)— Figure 5 presents a summary of the P_{cr} and P_{ult} values (defined in Figure 4) for SLC. When unanchored CFRP reinforcement was added, the capacity of concrete beams increased by 31% compared to the unstrengthened control. The capacity further increased in anchored specimens, ranging from 57% to 87%. The increase in capacity showed a positive correlation with the AR. Specimens with anchored bonded CFRP performed better than those with unbonded CFRP. The loss in capacity due to the CFRP being unbonded ranged from 30% to 40% compared to the corresponding bonded specimens. This loss in capacity exhibited an inverse correlation with the AR. The observed behaviors aligned well with the failure modes: specimens with 6.4-mm anchors failed due to anchor rupture at the anchor-CFRP junction, while the remaining anchored specimens exhibited CFRP rupture.

Accelerated Conditioning Protocol (ACP)— Figure 5 presents the ACP data. Additionally, to analyze the results more effectively, the ACP averages were normalized to the corresponding SLC averages to calculate *strength retention*, as shown in Figure 6. The introduction of ACP did not have a statistically significant impact on the capacity of both unstrengthened and strengthened (unanchored) beams. In a previous study (Tatar and Hamilton 2016b), the CFRP system used in this experiment exhibited a minimum bond capacity deterioration of 15%. However, in our study, we observed no loss in bond capacity, suggesting that the measures taken to minimize bond deterioration, such as slag replacement

and air entrainment, were successful. Overall, the P_{cr} values were unaffected by the presence of ACP across all experimental groups.

The most notable decrease in P_{ult} , amounting to 24% and 16%, was observed in beams with bonded and unbonded CFRP anchored with 6.4-mm anchors, respectively. These beams failed either due to anchor splay rupture or rupture at the anchor-CFRP junction, indicating deterioration of the anchors. Other test groups did not show significant capacity losses. Interestingly, specimens with unbonded CFRP and 9.5- or 12.7-mm anchors experienced an increase in capacity by 18% and 14% respectively. The reason behind this phenomenon remains unclear and is currently being investigated.

Figure 5. Summary of P_{cr} and P_{ult} values. [x-axis label legend: ‘A’ indicated ‘anchored;’ ‘B’ and ‘UB’ indicated bonded and unbonded, respectively; and the numeral indicates anchor diameter.]

Figure 6. Summary of strength retention values. [*x*-axis label legend: ‘A’ indicated ‘anchored;’ ‘B’ and ‘UB’ indicated bonded and unbonded, respectively; and the numeral indicates anchor diameter.]

CONCLUSIONS

The experimental program involved testing notched concrete beams with CFRP installed on the soffit in a three-point bending test setup. The beams were subjected to an accelerated conditioning protocol (ACP) involving water immersion at 50°C for 3,000 hours, while the control group was kept in standard laboratory conditions (SLC) with temperature maintained at 23 ± 3°C and relative humidity at 50 ± 10%. The primary focus was to examine the impact of anchorage ratio (AR), defined as the ratio of the equivalent laminate area of an anchor to the flexural laminate area, and the condition of the CFRP-concrete bond (bonded vs. unbonded) on the durability of the anchored CFRP systems. The key findings from the experimental evidence are as follows:

- Unbonded specimens in the SLC condition displayed a 30% to 40% lower capacity compared to the corresponding bonded specimens. This capacity loss demonstrated an inverse correlation with the AR.
- No loss in the bond capacity between CFRP and concrete was observed after undergoing ACP, suggesting that the implemented measures to minimize bond deterioration, such as slag replacement and air entrainment, were successful.
- The most significant reduction in P_{ult} , approximately 24% and 16%, was observed in beams with bonded and unbonded CFRP anchored with 6.4-mm anchors, respectively. These beams failed either due to anchor splay rupture or rupture at the anchor-CFRP junction, indicating deterioration of the anchors.
- Beams with larger anchors (9.5 mm and 12.7 mm) did not experience a loss in capacity but failed due to CFRP rupture.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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